

SECASSURED

Security Assurance-driven AI-based Security Services for Trustworthy Security Engineering from Left-to-Right

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<p>Abstract:</p> <p>This deliverable presents the Data Management Plan (DMP) established for the SECASSURED project, defining how data generated throughout the project will be managed. It outlines the processes and measures adopted to ensure compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and all relevant legal requirements. To guarantee that project data is openly accessible, interoperable, and reusable, the SECASSURED DMP adheres to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles as recommended by the European Commission, and enriches datasets with appropriate metadata to maximise their long-term usability.</p>		
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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the Data Management Plan (DMP) established for the SECASSURED project, defining how data generated throughout the project will be managed. It outlines the processes and measures adopted to ensure compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and all relevant legal requirements. To guarantee that project data is openly accessible, interoperable, and reusable, the SECASSURED DMP adheres to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles as recommended by the European Commission and enriches datasets with appropriate metadata to maximise their long-term usability.

The primary objectives of the SECASSURED DMP are to:

- ensure compliance with the Horizon Europe Open Data Access Guidelines.
- align with EU data management policies by providing open access to EU-funded research data.
- enable broad accessibility of project data to the research community, ultimately improving research efficiency and contributing to societal benefit.

This deliverable describes the types of data created or collected within the project and details their full lifecycle—from generation and processing to storage, sharing, and preservation. It specifies which datasets will be made openly accessible after project completion and the standards that will be used for data representation. Attention is given to the protection of personal data in accordance with GDPR, including ethical considerations, consent procedures, and the internal processes that SECASSURED will implement.

This SECASSURED DMP will be updated throughout the duration of the project to reflect new datasets, changes in management practices, or revisions of Consortium policies. The final version will provide a comprehensive overview of all SECASSURED datasets, confirm compliance with applicable data protection regulations, and ensure that all project-generated data is fully accessible and reusable.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
DMP	Data Management Plan
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
WP	Work Package
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
TLS	Transport Layer Security
VNA	Vector Network analyser
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
GA	Grant Agreement
EEA	European Economic Area

1 Introduction

1.1 SECASSURED in Brief

The overall objective of SECASSURED is to develop innovative and advanced AI-driven security engineering solutions (Figure 1), establishing a holistic assurance-driven digital-twins-based framework which is capable of:

- Enhancing security across software, hardware, and supply chains: SECASSURED will identify cybersecurity and regulatory risks while seamlessly integrating third-party components, including both commercial and open-source software.
- Providing scalable virtual environments for more automated security assessment: The project will enable scalable virtual environments to automate the security assessment of diverse system components, including AI modules, and ensure their secure integration.
- Continuous assurance-driven security engineering: SECASSURED will deliver AI-enabled security services to support continuous, assurance-driven security engineering across the entire system lifecycle.

This initiative sets the foundation for secure, continuous integration of third-party components, including AI modules, across the computing continuum, aligning with the European Commission's evolving security and privacy regulations and the vision for human-centred and trustworthy AI.

Figure 1 – SECASSUREC Concept architecture

1.2 Scope and Objective of this Deliverable

This Data Management Plan (DMP) provides an overview of the full lifecycle of research data generated within the SECASSURED project. The project is funded under the Horizon Europe programme (Grant Agreement No. 101225858) and has a duration of 36 months.

The purpose of this deliverable is to describe the types of data that will be collected during the project and to outline how these data will be stored, managed, published, distributed, and, when appropriate,

reused. By establishing clear data management procedures, the project aims to maximise societal impact and ensure a lasting legacy of the research conducted under European Commission funding. This DMP report identifies the datasets that SECASSURED will create, process, and share, and explains how these datasets align with the project's objectives and work package structure.

1.3 Relationship to Other SECASSURED Deliverables

Although the DMP is related to all Work Packages' tasks, it is relevant to highlight its relationship with WP12 and WP13 Dissemination and Exploitation tasks and deliverables D12.1, D12.2, and D13.1 - Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities.

The Data Management Plan defines how research data generated or collected during the project are handled, stored, shared and preserved, in line with Open Science and FAIR principles, while also addressing legal, ethical, GDPR and intellectual property constraints. The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation work package builds on these conditions to ensure that project results, including data-driven outputs, are communicated and disseminated to relevant stakeholders and exploited where appropriate. Dissemination and communication activities are therefore aligned with the data access conditions, embargo periods and licensing schemes defined in the Data Management Plan, ensuring that openness is balanced with the protection of sensitive information and exploitable results. In this way, the Data Management Plan provides the framework that enables effective, compliant and impact-oriented communication, dissemination and exploitation activities throughout the project lifecycle.

1.4 Deliverable Structure

The structure that this deliverable follow is:

- Section 1 is the introductory section of the deliverable
- Section 2 is the analysis of the Data Management Plan
- Section 3 is the description of the data sets per WP
- Section 4 outlines the FAIR principles and contributions to Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP)
- Section 5 reports any Ethics considerations related to SECASSURED's data
- Section 6 Summarizes the SECASSURED GDPR policy
- Section 7 Conclusions

2 SECASSURED Data Management Plan

The SECASSURED DMP outlines the full data management lifecycle for all data collected, processed, and generated during the project, as well as procedures that continue beyond its completion. It documents the data flows associated with specific use cases, provides structured reporting to support evaluation, and includes detailed information on:

- the handling of research data during the project and after its conclusion,
- the types of data to be collected, processed, and generated,
- the methodologies and standards that will be applied,
- the conditions under which data will be shared or made openly accessible, and
- the processes for data curation and long-term preservation, including post-project measures.

The SECASSURED project generates, processes, and manages a diverse range of data throughout its lifecycle, reflecting both technical and administrative activities. Proper management of these data is essential to ensure internal exploitation, secure sharing, and eventual dissemination, in full compliance with ethical, legal, and IPR requirements.

The following table provides a high-level mapping of data types to the corresponding Work Packages (WPs), their visibility levels, and alignment with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). Visibility levels indicate the scope of access for each data type:

- Public – freely accessible outside the consortium
- Restricted – shared externally under controlled conditions
- Internal – accessible only to SECASSURED partners
- Confidential – highly sensitive, limited to specific partners or roles

This framework ensures that data are effectively utilized within the project before publication, supporting analysis, validation, integration, and decision-making. At the same time, it facilitates discoverability, interoperability, and reusability in line with FAIR data management principles.

The table that follows presents an overview of the key data types, highlighting how each contributes to the project’s objectives and adherence to FAIR principles, while clarifying access rights and publication pathways.

Table 1 - SECASSURED Key Data types

WP	Data Type	Description	Visibility	FAIR Alignment
WP1 – Project Management	Documents	Project management documents (e.g. Project Handbook, Quality Plan, schedules)	Internal	F, I, R
	Documents	Progress & milestone reports (Periodic technical &	Restricted	F, A, I, R

		financial reporting)		
	Documents	Risk, ethics & IPR documentation (E.g.: Risk logs, ethics self-assessments, IPR records)	Confidential	F, R
	Documents	Meeting minutes & internal correspondence (Steering committee and WP coordination)	Internal	F, R
WP2 – Requirements & Use Cases	Documents	Use-case descriptions (Telecom, aeronautics, eHealth, smart charging)	Public (sanitized)	F, A, I, R
	Documents	Security, assurance, interoperability requirements	Internal	F, I, R
	Documents	Stakeholder analysis (e.g. User needs and system constraints)	Internal	F, I, R
	Documents	Scenario definitions (E.g.: Reference operational scenarios)	Restricted	F, I, R
WP3 – Architecture & Assurance	Documents	Architecture specifications: (e.g. System, data, and assurance architecture)	Restricted	F, I, R
	Model	Conceptual models & methodologies (E.g.: Security assurance and	Public (selected)	F, A, I, R

		digital twin models)		
	Source code	Interface & integration specifications (e.g.: APIs, data exchange definitions)	Internal	F, I, R
	documents	Standards mapping documentation (e.g. Alignment with ISO/IEC, EU standards)	Public	F, A, I, R
WP4 – Tools & Software	Source code	Source code & software components (e.g. AI assurance tools, libraries)	Internal / Restricted	F, I, R
	Text files	Configuration files & build scripts: (e.g. CI/CD and DevSecOps pipelines)	Internal	F, I, R
	Documents	Software documentation (e.g. User guides, developer manuals)	Public / Restricted	F, A, I, R
	Text files	Software quality metrics (e.g. Test coverage, quality indicators)	Internal	F, I, R
WP5 – Validation & Testing	Testing data	Testing datasets (e.g. Synthetic & scenario-based test data)	Internal	F, I, R
	Text files	Validation & performance results (e.g. Security assessments, KPIs)	Restricted	F, A, I, R
	Testing data		Internal	F, I, R

		Simulation & digital twin outputs (e.g. Virtual testing environment data)		
	Documents	Demonstration reports (e.g. Pilot and validation summaries)	Public (aggregated)	F, A, I, R
WP6 – Data Analysis & Evaluation	Documents	Analysis reports (e.g. Risk, assurance, and performance analyses)	Restricted	F, A, I, R
	Text files	Evaluation metrics (e.g. System effectiveness & compliance metrics)	Internal	F, I, R
	Text files	Impact assessment studies (e.g. Technical, societal, economic impact)	Public	F, A, I, R
	Testing data	Aggregated statistical results (e.g. Non-sensitive analytics)	Public	F, A, I, R
WP7 – Dissemination & Exploitation	Documents	Scientific publications (e.g. Journal & conference papers)	Public	F, A, I, R
	Documents	Whitepapers & policy briefs (e.g. Industry and research insights)	Public	F, A, I, R
	Documents	Presentations & training materials: (e.g. Slides, webinars, workshops)	Public	F, A, I, R

	Documents	Exploitation plans (e.g. Business and sustainability strategies)	Restricted	F, A, I, R
Cross-cutting	Text files	Metadata catalogues (e.g. Dataset descriptions, provenance records)	Internal	F, A, I, R
	Text files	FAIR compliance records (e.g. Metadata standards & mappings)	Public (summary)	F, A, I, R
	Text files	Data access logs (e.g. Access and usage tracking)	Confidential	F, R

2.1 Data life cycle

This section describes the data lifecycle in the SECASSURED project. This data lifecycle comprises next steps:

Figure 2.- Data Life cycle¹

¹ Figure generated by AI tool

2.1.1 Data Generation and creation

The Data Generation and Creation stage includes all datasets, project documentation, spreadsheets, software code, analysis outputs, and metadata produced or collected within SECASSURED. Data originate either from internal project activities, such as experiments, pilots, and software development, or from third-party providers, including external suppliers and consortium stakeholders.

Before any third-party data are integrated, a data sharing agreement or contract is established. This agreement defines the purpose of the data, permitted usage, access restrictions, licensing, and IPR conditions, ensuring that both the provider’s intent and the project’s objectives are clear from the outset. The presence of such an agreement serves as the primary indicator of whether the data can be used and processed within the project.

All data, internal or external, are collected in standardized formats and structured layouts to ensure compatibility and efficient processing by all project modules. Naming conventions, tagging, and documentation standards are applied consistently, and metadata is recorded to capture provenance, licensing, usage conditions, and purpose.

Data quality is assessed according to five key criteria:

Table 2 - Evaluation criteria for Data creation and/or collection

Performance Indicator	Means of verification	Target Values
Format	Compliance with existing standards of data exchange	CSV, XLS, XML, etc.
Availability and Readability	Whole package of data available, non-corruption, whole percentage collected (e.g. verifiable by hash functions)	100% received 100% accessible
Fit for Use	Data follow data compliancy for proper processing and review	100% usable by intended beneficiary/ies
Consistency and Completeness	Data are consistent and complete for the intended purpose	Including 100% of information for the intended purpose
Relation	Data following a precise relation to their purpose	100% purpose precision

2.1.2 Data processing and analysis

The Data Processing and Analysis stage covers the verification, organization, transformation, integration, and calibration of data by SECASSURED partners acting as data processors. Internal partners, including WP teams, analysts, and developers, handle data within secure consortium platforms and pilot environments, while third-party data are processed according to the permissions

and conditions defined in data sharing agreements. This ensures compliance with licensing, IPR, and intended use.

Processed data are harmonized and structured to maintain logical consistency, interoperability, and readiness for analysis, with metadata updated to capture processing steps, transformations, and provenance. Analytical methods are then applied to describe observations, detect patterns, derive insights, and produce documented outputs.

Specific evaluation criteria for this stage include:

Table 3 - Evaluation criteria for data processing and analysis

Performance Indicator	Means of verification	Target Values
Data logic	Data can be and are processed following a concise logic and approach	New and processed data follow precise data logic
Organization and Utility	Suitable content organization of data under processing	100% organized data
Validation	Ensuring that the data under processing are correct and relevant	100% validated and relevant data
Aggregation	Whenever multiple data need to be aggregated ensure that this is done in a concise approach	100% aggregate-able data
Transformation	Transformation of data to the proper format(s) for processing	Capability of data for transformation (if needed)
Calibration	Calibration of data for their intended purpose	Data properly calibrated

Responsible data sharing: If a partner identifies an error, inconsistency, or potential issue in any dataset, they must inform the relevant WP lead immediately. The WP leader coordinates corrections, updates metadata to reflect the issue, and, if applicable, issues a general notice of the problem to external users, without maintaining a list of recipients. This process ensures reliability, transparency, and trustworthiness of the data.

2.1.3 Data storage and archiving

The Data Storage and Archiving stage ensures that all SECASSURED data, including internal and third-party datasets, software, and documentation, are securely stored, preserved, and made discoverable for future use. Internal actors in SECASSURED project are responsible for storing data in secure repositories, cloud platforms, and pilot environments. Third-party data are stored according to the

permissions, retention terms, and conditions defined in the data sharing agreements, maintaining compliance with licensing, IPR, and GDPR requirements. Key considerations at this stage include maintaining the most up-to-date version of each dataset, unless previous versions are explicitly retained for reference. This stage also addresses measures to prevent accidental data loss, corruption, and unauthorized access. Furthermore, proper storage and archiving are essential to ensuring data reusability, a core principle of FAIR data management.

Specific evaluation criteria for this stage include:

Table 4 - Evaluation criteria for data storage archiving and secondary use of data

Performance Indicator	Means of verification	Target Values
Up to date	Ensuring that the stored data are up to date for the specific purpose and no later version exists	100% updated
Meta Data	Existence of meta data in stored files	Relevant metadata have been included into the archive per data set
Security (b)	Access control provided	Access control setup
Security (c)	Server is considered as safe enough (TLS connection protocol)	At least TLS connection configuration
Bandwidth	Control of server bandwidth	Effective storage server bandwidth > 2 MBPS
Expiration	Properly setting expiration dates for all data after which the data will be deleted	Expiration date noted

If errors are identified during storage or archiving, the same responsible reporting workflow applies: the WP lead coordinates corrections, updates metadata, and ensures that notices are issued to relevant users in line with sharing agreements.

2.1.4 Internal sharing and utilization

The Internal Sharing and Utilization stage focuses on the controlled exchange and use of SECASSURED data within the consortium. Internal actors, including WP teams, analysts, and project leads, access data through secure platforms, repositories, and pilot environments, ensuring compliance with project requirements and objectives. Third-party data are shared and utilized only according to the permissions and restrictions defined in the data sharing agreements, maintaining adherence to licensing, IPR, and GDPR obligations.

During this stage, data are made available to consortium partners for analysis, validation, integration, and decision-making. Metadata is used to facilitate findability, traceability, and interoperability, ensuring that datasets can be correctly interpreted and reused across WPs. The main objective is to ensure that data are shared under appropriate control mechanisms, safeguarding proprietary information and maintaining data integrity.

Specific evaluation criteria for this stage include:

Table 5 - Evaluation criteria for data publication and utilization

Performance Indicator	Means of verification	Target Values
Means-independent	Transferring of the data in a means-independent approach	100% means independent transferability
Security (a)	Data stored in a secure server	By minimum access control provided over a TLS protocol

If errors are identified during storage or archiving, the same responsible reporting workflow applies: the WP lead coordinates corrections, updates metadata, and ensures that notices are issued to relevant users in line with sharing agreements.

2.1.5 Data Publication and Dissemination

The Data Publication and Dissemination stage involves making SECASSURED data and outputs available outside the consortium, once internal utilization and validation are complete. Internal actors, including WP7 leads, dissemination teams, and task coordinators, manage the publication process. Third-party data can only be included or referenced externally if explicitly permitted in the corresponding data sharing agreements; otherwise, outputs derived from such data are aggregated, anonymized, or modified to prevent unauthorized disclosure.

This stage encompasses the preparation of scientific publications, whitepapers, policy briefs, demonstration reports, and metadata catalogs. All published data are accompanied by detailed metadata describing provenance, format, licensing, and usage restrictions to ensure FAIR compliance, supporting findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. Evaluation criteria include completeness and accuracy of published outputs, adherence to licensing and IPR requirements, proper anonymization or aggregation of sensitive information, and compliance with EC open-access guidelines.

If a published dataset or derived output is found to contain errors, the project implements the responsible data sharing workflow: metadata and repositories are updated, and a general notice may be issued publicly without requiring a list of recipients.

2.1.6 Data flows in SECASSURED

SECASSURED will integrate multiple research methodologies, including empirical user studies, design science, and data-driven research (Figure 3). Research, implementation, and validation activities will be conducted following modern DevOps, SecDevOps, and MLOps practices, using small, continuous

iterations throughout the project. Each iteration will introduce incremental improvements aligned with the overall project objectives.

Iterations may involve one or more of the following activities: use case definition, requirement analysis, data collection, tool design, AI model training, implementation deployment, use case application, and validation. Data acquisition activities explicitly distinguish between data generated within SECASSURED and data supplied by third-party actors, such as technology providers, infrastructure operators, or industrial stakeholders. Third-party data are integrated into the iterative flow only after verification of contractual terms, licensing, and intended usage, ensuring compliance with IPR, GDPR, and agreed data-sharing conditions. The project workforce will be organized into several technical or use-case-focused teams, structured according to DevOps principles. These teams independently conduct iterations in parallel, while interacting with external data providers and downstream users through controlled interfaces, such as agreed data exchange formats, metadata specifications, and access conditions.

Joint sprints involving multiple teams will be planned and executed as needed to support inter-task development, such as integration, cross-use-case application, and system-level validation.

The iterative process will be structured into three phases, with clearly defined, evaluable results at the end of each phase.

Figure 3 – Approach of SECASSURED project

Phase	Focus	Outputs
1. Inception (WP1-4) (M1-M6)	Define requirement; Design starting features of tools/services; Identify techniques, AI models, datasets, interaction between tools/services.	Requirement document, initial design of the tools and the framework. Demo: State-of-the-practice assurance-driven security engineering on sample scenarios, showing demands of assurance-driven security engineering.

<p>2. Proof of concept (M7-M18) (WP1-4)</p>	<p>Refine the requirement and use cases; Assess and select the effective (AI) approaches, set up AI pipelines per tool, train AI models with initial data/experimental environments; integrate all the tools in a minimal use case scenario</p>	<p>Initial resource management tools working on simplified scenarios; Sample assurance-driven security engineering practices identified from mock-up artifacts and reflected in AI decisions Demo: A minimal assurance-driven security engineering scenario working on a simplified environment.</p>
<p>3. Consolidated research & tools (M19-M36)(WP5-11)</p>	<p>Finalize product-relevant use case scenarios; Finalize the tools with trained AI models and effective pipelines, and apply them on the final use cases; Implement the integrated framework</p>	<p>Resource management tools with clear advantage beyond the SOTA; Assurance-driven security engineering practices from real artifacts reflected in decisions. Demo: Complete assurance-driven security engineering scenarios on production environments in all the UCs.</p>

The SECASSURED’s security services catalogue will be tested and validated, on 5 Use Cases (UCs) of data processing on the computing continuum. All the 5 UCs demand assurance-driven security engineering, from different perspectives:

- UC1: ORO provides broadband internet and mobile service in Romania and needs more assurance-driven security innovation for Telecom Software Development Life Cycle.
- UC2: ITP Aero - a global leader in aerospace propulsion - needs more security assurance for digitalization platform integration in Aerospace Industry.
- UC3: UIH and SPS need the improvement of the protection of prosumer cell operations and through them that of the grid by, validating devices and applications deployed, for Renewable Prosumer Energy.
- UC4: TellU provides eHealth services in a Software as a Service (SaaS) model that needs end to end security and privacy across the IoT, edge and cloud spaces.
- UC5: PPC needs the enhancement of the security of their Smart Charging Stations, especially including Supply Chain Security for AI Software.

The 5 UCs are deliberately selected to (1) cover the spectrum from enterprise groups (ORO, ITP Aero, PPC), SMEs (TellU, AROBS, UIH, SPS), to research-industry strong rooted connections (IDEKO-SAVVY, STF-TellU); (2) represent typical stakeholders in the security engineering and owners of critical industry (telecom, energy, healthcare, manufacturing); and (3) ensure each (AI-based) security services to be validated in at least 2 UCs.

In each of these stages, significant data will be created and managed following the rules described in this DMP.

2.2 Data management report

In order to ensure the compliance of this Data Management plan and a proper management of data elements by SECASSURED WP leaders (for each WP), the table in Annex I: Data Management report will act as a formal auditory.

2.3 Metadata

Each data component owner is responsible for applying the appropriate naming and tagging conventions as defined in the SECASSURED Project Handbook (see D14.1 Project Handbook). These conventions are explicitly aligned, where possible, with well-established and widely adopted industry standards to support effective data management. Their consistent application ensures that metadata can be reliably recorded, extracted, managed, and referenced, thereby supporting all aspects of data handling and utilization within SECASSURED.

SECASSURED places high importance on metadata provisioning and search capabilities, which serve as the primary channels for enabling data interoperability. Interoperability considerations are detailed in Section 3, Data Sets in SECASSURED, and summarized in Section 3.1, SECASSURED Data Description per WP, with respect to data usage and utilization. The adoption of clearly defined naming conventions, standardized file tagging, and robust search mechanisms—based on recognized industry practices—is essential for maximizing internal data interoperability and facilitating structured management of project data assets.

It is important to note that data interoperability is considered only for internal purposes within SECASSURED, including data reuse, exchange, and general utilization. For data interoperability outside the consortium, SECASSURED will strictly follow IPR rules to ensure that no project foreground is released. For additional information on external data sharing in compliance with IPR, see Section 6, General Data Protection Policy (GDPR), of this report.

Regarding filename conventions, the consortium aims to use commonly accepted formats such as .XML and .XLS(X) to maximize interoperability. Where appropriate, SECASSURED will explore the adoption of additional internationally recognized standards for both data and software. Metadata standards under consideration include ISO 19115 (for GIS data), ISO 14721 (Open Archival Information Systems, OAIS), and ISO 16363 (audit and trustworthiness of digital repositories), supporting long-term digital data management. Additionally, software-related standards, such as ISO 25010 (software engineering quality) and SQuaRE (Systems and Software Quality Requirements and Evaluation), will be investigated to ensure quality and interoperability of project-produced software.

3 Data sets in SECASSURED and the SECASSURED demonstrations

This section outlines the concepts and purposes of data collection within the context of the project's work breakdown structure (WBS). It details the methods of data collection, the types of data to be collected, and the formats in which data will be recorded, based on input from the respective WP leaders.

This section will be continuously updated and more details on the research data will be available at later stages of the project.

The following subsections provide a description of the data that will be created and/or distributed for each SECASSURED work package. Data types may include narrative texts, numerical datasets, images, audio and video files, as well as internal and external reports.

3.1 SECASSURED data description per WP

This section describes the data produced or processed at each WP and elaborates on a number of factors for each of the involved data objects. Each WP’s introductory subsection addresses the intended purpose of use of the provided data from the Data Owner’s perspective and relates them to the SECASSURED’s objectives while the table structure below elaborates for each data element, the following information:

- Short description of data content and type
- Data origin/source (where the data come from)
- Data format
- Confidentiality level (Public, Project consortium, data processor(s), Research purpose))
- Processing/Usage preconditions (restrictions)

3.1.1 WP1 – Requirement, architectures and use case definition

Table 6 – WP1 data mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Interface & API specifications for integrating tools into the SecureFlow framework.	Produced by AST in collaboration with technical partners during integration design.	JSON, YAML, OpenAPI specs, PDF documentation.	Confidential – consortium only	Access restricted to authorized members; stored in secure project repositories.
Configuration files and deployment artifacts (CI/CD pipelines).	Generated by AST during platform integration, deployment, and orchestration.	YAML, JSON, Dockerfiles , shell scripts.	Confidential – consortium only	Access limited to technical partners; used solely for project integration activities.
Synthetic & Simulated Test Datasets and Security Reports.	Generated by AST via SonarQube (Static Analysis).	JSON, CSV, SonarQube HTML/PDF reports , XML.	Confidential – consortium only	Synthetic data only; used exclusively for testing, validation, and AI training.
Integration and system logs (Performance Telemetry).	Automatically generated by K3s Edge Agents and the platform during testing phases.	Log files (.log), text files, Prometheus data.	Confidential – consortium only	Access restricted to authorized partners; contains no real operational or personal data.
Validation and performance testing results for the Security Services Catalogue.	Produced by AST and partners during system-wide integration validation.	PDF reports, Excel spreadsheets, structured data.	Confidential – consortium only	Used for internal evaluation and reporting; shared within consortium under agreed procedures.
Technical documentation and integration guidelines for onboarding.	Produced by AST for internal partner use and Open Call participant support.	PDF, Markdown, text documentation.	Confidential (Internal)	Internal documentation; selected materials shared with Open Call participants under specific conditions.
Deliverable D1.3 Continuous integration environment and practice	Task 1.4 deliverable	Report – doc & PDF	Confidential	

3.1.2 WP2 – Assurance model and interpretation service

Table 7 - WP2 data mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
EU Regulations and standards (e.g. EU AI Act; CRA)	Public standards bodies; licensed publishers	Narrative and formative text	Public	
Industrial, sector-specific norms and standards	e.g. IEC 62443 Part 4-2, IEEE 1686, and IEC 62351	Narrative and formative text	Both Public and organizational	Respect licensing/NDAs

			policies can be considered	
System/product information	Public documents	Narrative text	Public	
System functional requirements	Public documents	Narrative text	public	
API specifications and data schemas	WP2 outcome	OpenAPI (JSON/YAML)	Public	-
CSAM taxonomy/ontology	WP2 outcome (CSAM)	TBD	Public	
Evidence (Link evidence to requirements)	CSAM output	TBD	Confidential	
Sector-to-standard mapping	secInterp information	Database	Confidential	
Extracted technical requirements checklists	secInterp information	Database	Confidential	Respect licensing
OSCAL catalogs, profiles, templates (secSAC) — structured controls	WP2 outcome (secSAC)	OSCAL	Public	Conform to OSCAL schemas
Security Assurance Case instances (SACs)	secSAC outputs	OSCAL	Confidential	
WP Report (Deliverable D2.1)	WP2 outcome	narrative text	Public	
Blogposts and Newsletters	WP2 outcome	website	Public	

3.1.3 WP3 - SEDEVTWIN & DEV security service

WP3 generates and processes data to support the development and validation of security development and assurance services aligned with the objectives of SECASSURED. The data are used to enable the assessment of software components and systems with respect to security vulnerabilities, misconfigurations, and compliance with security standards and regulations. WP3 activities rely on software artefacts, security requirement checklists, vulnerability annotations, runtime logs and traces, simulation outputs, and AI model artefacts to develop services for digital twin (secDevTwin), non-compliance assessment (secNCD), vulnerability discovery and repair (secVDR), assurance of AI components (secAssure4AI), and security simulation (secSIM).

Table 8 - WP3 data mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Project Deliverable D3.1	WP3 project outcome	Report (Doc and PDF)	Public	Public dissemination according to project policy.
Scientific papers related to WP3 activities	WP3 project outcome	PDF	Emphasis on Public (Open Access); some subscription-based publications possible	Shared after the successful publication on the targeted conferences/journals.
Blogposts and Newsletters	WP3 project outcome	Website content	Public	No confidential or sensitive information included.
Machine Learning models released as research and development outcomes	WP3 project outcome	.h5 and/or .pt etc.	Public	Shared after publication or project completion.
Security requirements checklists used for compliance assessment (secNCD)	secInterp (WP2) output. Standardization organizations (e.g., ETSI)	JSON containing narrative and formative text	Both Public and Private standards can be considered.	-
Data generated through the secNCD workflow: expert inputs, Q&A interactions, and non-compliance results	Generated by secNCD	JSON, narrative text	Confidential	Access restricted to authorised users.

Vulnerability-related datasets needed for training and evaluating the vulnerability discovery and repair models for the construction of the SECASSURED vulnerability module (secVDR).	GitHub, HuggingFace	CSV, JSON	Public	Used in accordance with dataset licenses.
Source code repositories needed for the analysis of the vulnerability discovery and repair mechanisms (secVDR).	GitHub, GitLab, pilots	Source code files, repositories	Public and private repositories	-
Vulnerability detection results (locations, categories, scores)	Generated by secVDR discovery services	JSON	Confidential	-
Vulnerability repair recommendations and/or patches	Generated by secVDR repair services	JSON, code snippets	Confidential	-
Runtime execution logs, system traces, monitoring outputs, and security-related telemetry generated during dynamic analysis, vulnerability testing, and scenario-based validation activities within SecDevTwin.	Generated during WP3 dynamic analysis, runtime monitoring, and testing activities (including simulated or pilot-derived environments).	Structured and semi-structured log formats (e.g., log files, JSON traces, monitoring exports, event streams).	Confidential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - May contain system configuration details or security-sensitive metadata - Stored in secured internal repositories - Access restricted to authorized consortium members - Personal data, if any, will be minimized, anonymized, or excluded - Not publicly shared unless fully anonymized and stripped of sensitive information
Security simulation outputs	secSIM (WP3) output	JSON, CSV, log	Confidential	Used only in controlled simulation environments
Structured representations of software components, architectural dependencies, deployment configurations, and security-relevant system properties used within the SecDevTwin environment.	Generated and maintained during SecDevTwin design and development (WP3), based on pilot architectures and synthetic or controlled test datasets.	Machine-readable structured formats (e.g., JSON, YAML, XML, graph models, configuration manifests).	Confidential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Used internally to simulate and validate security engineering processes - May contain architecture details and supply-chain dependency information - Access limited to consortium partners under the Consortium Agreement - Only generalized schemas/templates may be released as open artifacts
AI component assessment data (secAssure4AI): robustness, explainability, fairness, and safety metrics	Generated during the assessment of AI models	JSON, CSV, reports	Confidential	Used internally to assess the quality of SecAssured AI models
AI models that are going to be assessed (secAssure4AI) in respect of their security and overall trustworthiness	Developed in SecAssured component and other shard by UC provider	.h5 and/or .pt etc.	Confidential	Used internally to assess the quality of SecAssured AI models
AI attack and defence evaluation datasets	Generated during the operation of SecAssure4AI component	JSON, CSV	Public if such datasets can be used by others (the datasets are expected to be directly connected to use cases)	Used exclusively for research and evaluation in controlled environments
Vulnerability classification metadata using widely accepted security standards such as Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE) IDs for describing vulnerability categories	Generated by secVDR discovery services	CWE-IDs included in the JSON report of secVDR	Confidential	CWE taxonomy used in accordance with MITRE terms of use.
MITRE ATT&CK taxonomy: SecSIM will simulate different scenarios (topology change, new service, service decommissioning, attacks, mitigations etc.). Attacks are simulated using AttSecSim from WP4 following MITRE ATTACK taxonomy and	Generated by secSIM (WP3) during controlled simulation activities; attack scenarios executed using AttSecSim (WP4); mitigation workflows provided via AISecSOAR (WP4).	MITRE ATT&CK technique references (TIDs); OASIS CACAO v2 playbook format (JSON)	Confidential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Used exclusively within controlled simulation environments. - MITRE ATT&CK taxonomy referenced according to its public usage terms.

mitigations are relying on AISecSOAR presenting the playbooks using OASIS CACAO v2 standard.				
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3.1.4 WP4 - SECOPSTWIN & OPS SECURITY SERVICES

Table 9 - WP4 data mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Project Deliverable D4.1	WP4 project outcome	Report (Doc and PDF) and software (docker image and/or open source code files)	Public	Public dissemination according to project policy.
Scientific papers related to WP4 activities	WP4 project outcome	PDF	Emphasis on Public (Open Access); some subscription-based publications possible	Shared after the successful publication on the targeted conferences/journals.
Blogposts and Newsletters	WP4 project outcome	Website content	Public	No confidential or sensitive information included.
AI models released as research and development outcomes	WP4 project outcome	.h5 and/or .pt etc.	Public	Shared after publication or project completion.
Runtime system monitoring data (logs, metrics, events) used by SecOpsTwin	Critical Infrastructures, monitoring tools, sensors, partner testbeds	JSON, CSV, time-series DB, log files	Confidential (may include system-sensitive information)	Access restricted to consortium partners; anonymisation/pseudonymisation applied where required
Digital Twin configuration and model data (system topology, dependencies, DT parameters)	SecOpsTwin design activities, existing DT frameworks from partners	JSON, YAML, XML, model files	Confidential	Used only for research and validation within SecAssured; not shared externally
Security reports generated by SecOpsTwin	SecOpsTwin security monitoring service	JSON, txt	Public (if generated on synthetic data) and maybe Confidential (if it includes real, sensitive information)	Access restricted to consortium partners; anonymisation/pseudonymisation applied where required
Synthetic attack and incident datasets generated by GAN/LLM models	secAttSIM generation service	JSON, CSV, PCAP (if network-related)	Public and maybe Confidential depending on the content criticality	Fully synthetic; no real attacker or system-identifying data
Network traffic and monitoring data for anomaly detection	MTI Monitoring Framework (MMT), testbeds, SecOpsTwin outputs	PCAP, JSON, CSV, time-series	Public and maybe Confidential depending on the content criticality	Access controlled; data minimisation and anonymisation applied
Labeled anomaly and attack datasets (realistic or synthetic)	secAttSIM outputs, partner datasets	CSV, JSON	Public	Used only for training and evaluation of secAnoD models
Root cause analysis and detection explanations	secAnoD analysis components	JSON, text, structured reports	Confidential	No personal data; shared only within SecAssured
Incident alerts and detection events	secAnoD, external detectors, SecOpsTwin	JSON, STIX/TAXII	Confidential	Restricted to authorized SOC and project partners

Response playbooks, workflows, and orchestration policies	Shuffle platform, secAISOAR development	YAML, JSON	Public and maybe Confidential depending on the content criticality	If intellectual property of partners, no external redistribution
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3.1.5 WP5 – CONSOLIDATION OF RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT OF SERVICES

Since WP5 (M19-M34) builds upon and consolidates the research and development outcomes from WP2, WP3, and WP4 (M1-M18), the data used in these earlier work packages is carried forward into WP5. Rather than duplicating detailed metadata (e.g., data formats, confidentiality levels, and access restrictions) in this section, the WP5 data mapping references the data mappings in these WPs, where this information is comprehensively documented.

Table 10 - WP5 data mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Project Deliverables D5.1 and D5.2	WP5 project outcomes	Report (Doc and PDF) and software (docker image and/or open source code files)	Public	Public dissemination according to project policy.
Scientific papers related to WP5 activities	WP5 project outcome	PDF	Emphasis on Public (Open Access); some subscription-based publications possible	Shared after the successful publication on the targeted conferences/journals.
Blogposts and Newsletters	WP5 project outcome	Website content	Public	No confidential or sensitive information included.
Data used within WP2 remains under WP5 for the continuation of the research work and development of CSAM, standard interpretation Service and assurance cases	WP2	See Table 7 - WP2 data mapping	See Table 7 - WP2 data mapping	See Table 7 - WP2 data mapping
Data used within WP3 remains under WP5 for the continuation of the research work and development of SecDevTwin and Dev tools	WP3	See Table 8 - WP3 data mapping	See Table 8 - WP3 data mapping	See Table 8 - WP3 data mapping
Data used within WP4 remains under WP5 for the continuation of the research work and development of SecOpsTwin and Ops tools	WP4	See Table 9 - WP4 data mapping	See Table 9 - WP4 data mapping	See Table 9 - WP4 data mapping

3.1.6 WP6 – integrated SECASSURED security catalogue & platform

Table 11 - WP6 data mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
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Interface & API specifications for integrating tools into the SecureFlow framework.	Produced by AST in collaboration with technical partners during integration design.	JSON, YAML, OpenAPI specs, PDF documentation.	Confidential – consortium only	Access restricted to authorized members; stored in secure project repositories.
Configuration files and deployment artifacts (CI/CD pipelines).	Generated by AST during platform integration, deployment, and orchestration.	YAML, JSON, Dockerfiles , shell scripts.	Confidential – consortium only	Access limited to technical partners; used solely for project integration activities.
Synthetic & Simulated Test Datasets and Security Reports.	Generated by AST via SonarQube (Static Analysis).	JSON, CSV, SonarQube HTML/PDF reports , XML.	Confidential – consortium only	Synthetic data only; used exclusively for testing, validation, and AI training.
Integration and system logs (Performance Telemetry).	Automatically generated by K3s Edge Agents and the platform during testing phases.	Log files (.log), text files, Prometheus data.	Confidential – consortium only	Access restricted to authorized partners; contains no real operational or personal data.
Validation and performance testing results for the Security Services Catalogue.	Produced by AST and partners during system-wide integration validation.	PDF reports, Excel spreadsheets, structured data.	Confidential – consortium only	Used for internal evaluation and reporting; shared within consortium under agreed procedures.
Technical documentation and integration guidelines for onboarding.	Produced by AST for internal partner use and Open Call participant support.	PDF, Markdown, text documentation.	Confidential (Internal)	Internal documentation; selected materials shared with Open Call participants under specific conditions.

3.1.7 WP7 – use case 1 – telecom

Table 12 - WP7 data mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
SecDevTwin assurance evidence and findings	SECASSURED SecDevTwin integrated in the Smart Tracking SDLC	Structured artefacts (.json/.xml), findings (.csv/.json/.sarif), reports (.pdf)	Sensitive	Treat as sensitive considering that the Smart Tracking application is commercial
Orange Telco Cloud IaaS operational/ security logs	ORO Telco Cloud IaaS hosting environment for Smart Tracking	.log/.json platform logs, access records (.csv), audit reports (.pdf)	Sensitive	Treat as sensitive considering that Orange Telco Cloud IaaS platform is commercial
SOC/SIEM security events and incident artefacts	ORO SOC/SIEM processes/tools used during WP7/UC1 validation	Event exports (.json/.csv), incident notes (.pdf/.docx)	Sensitive	Strict access control; anonymise personal identifiers; export only fields needed for validation/reporting
SecOpsTwin anomaly analytics outputs	SECASSURED operational analytics over UC1 telemetry/logs in ORO environment	Alerts/events (.json/.csv), simulation outputs (.json/.csv), reports (.pdf)	Sensitive/Public	Share aggregated results when possible; keep raw streams in controlled environments
Smart Tracking SDLC artefacts and repository/pipeline metadata	ORO + AROBS SDLC toolchain and code repositories for Smart Tracking	Repo exports, .csv/.json metadata, build artefacts (.zip), reports (.pdf)	Sensitive	Access-controlled sharing with the consortium

3.1.8 WP8 – use case 2 – manufacturing

Table 13 - WP8 data mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Project Deliverable D8.1	WP8 project outcome	Report (Doc and PDF)	Confidential	Public dissemination according to project policy.
Scientific papers related to WP8 activities	WP8 project outcome	PDF	Emphasis on Public (Open Access); some subscription-based publications possible	Shared after the successful publication on the targeted conferences/journals.
SecDevTwin assurance evidence and findings	SECASSURED SecDevTwin integrated in the Smart Tracking SDLC	Structured artefacts (.json/.xml), findings (.csv/.json/.sarif), reports (.pdf)	Sensitive	Treat as sensitive considering that the Smart Tracking application is commercial
Sector-to-standard mapping	secInterp output	TBD	Confidential	
Extracted technical requirements checklists	secInterp output	TBD	Confidential	
OSCAL catalogs, profiles, templates (secSAC) — structured controls	secSAC output	OSCAL	Confidential	Conform to OSCAL schemas
Security requirements checklists used for compliance assessment (secNCD)	secInterp output. Standardization organizations (e.g., ETSI)	JSON containing narrative and formative text	Confidential	-
Data generated through the secNCD workflow: expert inputs, Q&A interactions, and non-compliance results	secNCD output	JSON, narrative text	Confidential	Access restricted to authorised users.
AI attack and defence evaluation datasets	Generated during the operation of SecAssure4AI component	JSON, CSV	Public if such datasets can be used by others (the datasets are expected to be directly connected to use cases)	Used exclusively for research and evaluation in controlled environments
Incident alerts and detection events	secAnoD output	JSON, STIX/TAXII	Confidential	Restricted to authorized SOC and project partners
Synthetic attack and incident datasets generated by GAN/LLM models	secAttSIM generation service	JSON, CSV, PCAP (if network-related)	Public and maybe Confidential depending on the content criticality	Fully synthetic; no real attacker or system-identifying data
Savvy platform information documentation manual	Internal Documentation	Pdf	Sensitive	Docker environment know-how

3.1.9 WP9 – use case 3 – renewable energy prosumer

WP9 focuses on the development and validation of the SECASSURED4Energy use case, which demonstrates assurance-driven security engineering in a renewable prosumer energy cell environment. Activities include the design of the use case architecture, integration of SECASSURED security services (WP2-WP6), validation of identity and access management mechanisms, testing of software and hardware components, and execution of security evaluation and stress-testing scenarios.

During these activities, architectural documentation, validation results, monitoring data, configuration artefacts, and security assessment outputs will be generated and analysed. Most datasets will be technical and operational in nature and will be shared within the consortium in controlled form.

Table 14 – WP9 data mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Prosumer cell architecture design documents.	UIH WP9 use case design activities	.pdf, .docx	Project consortium	Internal project usage only
Validation reports, stress-testing results, and performance evaluation of SECASSURED tools.	WP9 validation activities	.pdf, .docx, .csv	Project consortium	Shareable within consortium
Operational logs, device telemetry, and runtime monitoring outputs used for security validation.	Pilot prosumer cell environment	.json/.csv/.log	Sensitive	Access-controlled; anonymisation where applicable
Security assessment outputs, vulnerability findings, anomaly detection results, simulation outputs.	SECASSURED modules integrated in WP9 pilot	.json/.csv, .pdf	Sensitive / Project consortium	Aggregated results may be shared; raw data remains in controlled environments
Identity and access management validation results and configuration artefacts.	IAM security assessment activities (UIH + SPS)	.json/.pdf	Sensitive	Restricted access due to security relevance

3.1.10 WP10 – use case 4 – healthcare

Table 15 – WP10 data mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Project Deliverable DD10.1	WP10 project outcome	Report (Doc and PDF)	Confidential	Public dissemination according to project policy.
physiological measurements and health monitoring data	Gateway (edge device)	.xml	Confidential	For project consortium
Tellu Gateway monitoring metrics	SECASSURED SecDevTwin	.xml	Project Consortium	N/A
Device registration records, authentication events, certificate validation logs	Gateway / Onboarding service	JSON / log files	Confidential	Internal use only; may be shared in anonymized form for evaluation
Tellu Gateway Update packages metadata, version history	Gateway	JSON / log files	Project consortium	For project consortium

3.1.11 WP11 – use case 5 – smart charging stations

Table 16 – WP11 data mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Charging history from the e-mobility infrastructure, particularly from the EV charging stations, such as time and kWh provided in each charging session.	E-mobility department of PPC	CSV	Confidential, with restricted on a need-to-know basis access.	Anonymisation required to redact PII.
Network traffic from the EV charging stations, including traffic traces of OCPP 1.6/2.0.1	E-mobility department of PPC or laboratory infrastructure belonging to PPC Group or K3Y	PCAP	Confidential with restricted on a need-to-know basis access, if the dataset comes from the e-mobility department.	Potential need for anonymisation to redact PII.

Additional open data (e.g., weather data), to be used in conjunction to the charging history dataset.	To be determined	CSV, JSON	Confidential, only within the consortium	N/A
Prediction results from the AI toolset for e-mobility, including classification assessments, forecasting and clustering results.	AI toolset for e-mobility	CSV, JSON	Confidential, only within the consortium	N/A
AI model artifacts used by the AI toolset for e-mobility (e.g., pretrained models, scalars, encoders etc)	AI toolset for e-mobility	H5, JOBLIB	Confidential, only within the consortium	N/A
Explainability reports from K3Explainer	K3Explainer tool of K3Y	JSON	Confidential, only within the consortium	N/A
Source code of the AI toolset for e-mobility	AI toolset for e-mobility	Python code	Confidential, only within the consortium	N/A
D11.1 report	WP11 validation activities	.docx, .pdf	Confidential, only within the consortium	N/A
Data evidence generated during the validation activities, including operational logs from the SECASSURED tools, performance evaluation, KPI measurements, video recordings.	WP11 validation activities	JSON, .docx, .mp4	Confidential, only within the consortium	N/A

3.1.12 WP12 – dissemination and exploitation part 1. Awareness

Table 17 – WP12 data mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Name and email	Newsletter subscription, webinar registration	Text – CSV, xlsx	Sensitive – purpose bound (newsletter sending, disseminating webinar information)	GDPR compliance
Questionnaires	Custom made for SECASSURED	docx	Public	Contributors ' details either anonymised or simply consolidated
Website traffic metrics	Google Analytics	Report download in Pdf, CSV, xlsx	Private – no Personally Identifiable Information (PII) stored	Setup of Google Tag on website
Social media metrics	LinkedIn Page Analytics	Report download in Pdf, CSV, xlsx	Anonymized visitor data	-
Photo, images, video	Retrieved during physical or virtual project events, Custom made for SECASSURED	Common formats for pictures (jpg, png, ...) and videos (asf, avi, mpeg)	Public	Explicit consent received from appearing participants, Lawful use-rights granted from media owners
Posters, flyers	Custom made for SECASSURED	Pdf	Public	Design agreed by Project consortium
Website, Social media	LinkedIn, Twitter, Web		Public	Design agreed by Project consortium Contents agreed with involved partners.

List of Standards Developing Organizations (SDOs) and Technical Committees (TCs)	Publicly available information	Text - List	Public	-
SDOs and TCs memberships from partners	Partners information	Text – CSV, xlsx	Public	-
Presentations (workshops, conferences...)	Custom made for SECASSURED	Pdf, pptx	Public	SECASSURED template needs to be used. Contents agreed with involved partners. Acknowledgements to EU funding is compulsory
Scientific publications	SECASSURED outputs	pdf	Public	Open Access Contents agreed with involved partners. Acknowledgements to EU funding is compulsory
Key Exploitable Results and other project results	Result owners	Text – CSV, xlsx	Public	Protection of IPR (e.g., patents), or legitimate commercial interests can restrict public access.
Project Deliverable D12.1	Detailed plan of the project's dissemination, exploitation and communication effort	Report (Doc and PDF)	Public	Public dissemination according to project policy.
Project Deliverable D12.2	Report of D&E&C activities and achievements with updated plan for the second period	Report (Doc and PDF)	Sensitive	Restrictive dissemination according to project policy.

3.1.13 WP13 – dissemination and exploitation part 2: impact

Table 18 – WP13 data mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Name and email	Newsletter subscription, webinar registration	Text – CSV, xlsx	Sensitive – purpose bound (newsletter sending, disseminating webinar information)	GDPR compliance
Questionnaires	Custom made for SECASSURED	docx	Public	Contributors' details either anonymised or simply consolidated
Website traffic metrics	Google Analytics	Report download in Pdf, CSV, xlsx	Private – no Personally Identifiable Information (PII) stored	Setup of Google Tag on website
Social media metrics	LinkedIn Page Analytics	Report download in Pdf, CSV, xlsx	Anonymized visitor data	-
Photo, images, video	Retrieved during physical or virtual project events, Custom made for SECASSURED	Common formats for pictures (jpg, png, ...) and videos (asf, avi, mpeg)	Public	Explicit consent received from appearing participants, Lawful use-rights granted from media owners
Posters, flyers	Custom made for SECASSURED	Pdf	Public	Design agreed by Project consortium
Website, Social media	LinkedIn, Twitter, Web		Public	Design agreed by Project consortium Contents agreed with involved partners.
List of Standards Developing Organizations (SDOs) and Technical Committees (TCs)	Publicly available information	Text - List	Public	-
SDOs and TCs memberships from partners	Partners information	Text – CSV, xlsx	Public	-

Presentations (workshops, conferences...)	Custom made for SECASSURED	Pdf, pptx	Public	SECASSURED template needs to be used. Contents agreed with involved partners. Acknowledgements to EU funding is compulsory
Scientific publications	SECASSURED outputs	pdf	Public	Open Access Contents agreed with involved partners. Acknowledgements to EU funding is compulsory
Key Exploitable Results and other project results	Result owners	Text – CSV, xlsx	Public	Protection of IPR (e.g., patents), or legitimate commercial interests can restrict public access.
Project Deliverable D13.1	Final report of D&E&C achievements, with exploitation plan for 5 years after the project	Report (Doc and PDF)	Sensitive	Restrictive dissemination according to project policy.

3.1.14 WP14 – project management part1

Table 19 – WP14 data mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Project handbook and quality plan (D14.1), including project routines, quality procedures, initial risks	Based on GA/CA and consortium inputs	docx, pdf	Sensitive	Internal use only; governed by GA/CA; may include contact/role info; access restricted to partners
Interim project report (D14.3) includes summary of project operations and achievements	Compiled from WP leader inputs and partner reporting	docx, pdf	Sensitive	Internal use only; based on partner reporting; may include performance/budget/progress details; access restricted to partners
Project governance documentation, including GA meeting agendas/minutes, decisions, action lists, etc.	Consortium inputs, General Assembly representatives	docx, pdf	Sensitive	Internal use only; may contain personal data (names/roles); access restricted to partners
Risk register and mitigation tracking for project management risks	Based on GA/CA and consortium inputs	xlsx, docx, pdf	Sensitive	Internal use only; access restricted to partners; used as input to D14.1 and then continuously updated and monitored
Deliverable quality controls, including filled out review templates, review notes, acceptance status, etc.	Assigned internal reviewers	docx	Sensitive	Internal use only; access restricted to partners
Advisory Board setup and meeting material, including Advisory Board invitations, agendas, minutes, feedback summaries.	Technical manager, Advisory Board members	docx, pdf	Sensitive	Internal use only; may include external expert names, contact info and feedback; access restricted to partners; share on need-to-know basis
EC communication and review material, including amendment drafts, review planning and feedback, correspondence logs etc.	SINTEF (Coordinator)	docx, pdf, email exports	Sensitive	Internal use only; relevant to the contract; access limited to coordinator/authorized roles in the consortium

3.1.15 WP15 – project management part2

Table 20 – WP15 data mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
AI robustness assurance report (D15.1)	AALTO, AI Committee inputs	docx, pdf	Public	Public dissemination per deliverable list; ensure no confidential datasets or sensitive partner information is included
Final project report (D15.2) describing overall project operation and results	SINTEF (Coordinator), based on overall	docx, pdf	Sensitive	Internal use only; based on partner inputs; may include consolidated results, progress, and management

	operation and results of all WPs			information; access restricted to partners
AI Committee governance material, including committee procedures, meeting minutes, review notes	AALTO, AI Committee including internal and external experts	docx, pdf	Sensitive	Internal use only; may reference training data checks, bias considerations, and impact assessments
AI robustness review artefacts/results, including reviews of AI plans, explainability assessments, footprint/cost notes, etc.	AI Committee	docx, pdf	Sensitive	Internal use only; may contain sensitive evaluation content; to be shared only with relevant WPs/roles
Ethics, societal responsibility, gender equality, and environmental monitoring records (e.g., via continuous project risk assessment)	SINTEF, partner inputs	xlsx, docx, pdf	Sensitive	Internal use only; aligned with GA/CA obligations; GDPR considerations if any personal data appears; links to DMP updates

3.2 WP leaders’ responsibilities and allocation of resources

The work packages (WPs) of the SECASSURED project encompass all relevant resources, including technical effort, WP management, and the management of associated data. WP14 and WP15 hold overall responsibility for data management and lifecycle monitoring for all datasets created, collected, shared, or processed throughout the project.

To ensure compliance with the data management processes described for each WP in this DMP, the following SECASSURED-wide measures will be applied:

- WP leaders are responsible for ensuring that their work packages adhere to the data management specifications outlined in this DMP.
- The Project Manager of each partner organization is responsible for overseeing DMP-related activities and will serve as the point of contact for any DMP-related issues within the team.
- Data owners hold ultimate responsibility for complying with the requirements of the SECASSURED DMP and for adhering to applicable GDPR and data protection policies.
- The Project Manager, together with the primary contact from each partner, must ensure that all personnel involved in the project have read the DMP and implement its principles in their work.

4 Fair data management and the ORDP

Following EC guidelines related to FAIR data management (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reused data), in the SECASSURED project, data will be created, acquired and collected in all SECASSURED's Work Packages and will include among others: Reports (internal or external to SECASSURED) in text, MS Word and other text files, MS XLS or other spreadsheets, MS Power Point files (presentations), audio files (.wav, .mp3, etc.), multimedia files (video recording and other), specification documents (text), software application source code files, software application executable, files, other observation material, survey questionnaires and data, factsheets, project images, etc.

The next section describes the naming conventions followed for FAIR data management and contribution to open data research, data identification and searching, as well as meta-data provisions and data reusability.

4.1 FAIR data management

SECASSURED will implement several actions described below to act in accordance with the FAIR principles.

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

- The datasets will have very rich metadata to facilitate the findability. Open data format (csv, xml) will be used.
- All the datasets will have Digital Object Identifiers provided by the public repository (GitLab and ZENODO: <https://zenodo.org/communities/secassured>).
- The reference used for the dataset will follow the format: "SECASSURED_Process_Datatype_XX" (XX: identifier to be added for similar datasets).
- The standards for metadata will be defined for each dataset as described in Section 2.4.

Making data openly accessible:

- The datasets that will be openly available will be described according to Table 13.
- The datasets for evaluation will be accessible via SECASSURED's Microsoft Teams Server.
- The datasets will be made available using a public repository (GitLab and ZENODO: <https://zenodo.org/communities/secassured>) after the project.
- Table 13 and Table 1 will be used to explain the methods or software used to access the data. Basically, no software is needed to access the data.
- The data and their associated metadata will be hosted in a public repository or in an institutional repository.

Making data interoperable:

- The metadata vocabularies, standards and methodologies will depend on the public repository and use the recommendations of section 2.4.
- The SECASSURED will define a common data format or reuse an existing one. This work is being developed in close collaboration with Task 6.4 Security, Data Management and Governance with the goal to follow a single format across the project.

Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

- All data producers will license their data to allow the widest reuse possible. Examples of licenses are available at <https://opendefinition.org/licenses/>.
- By default, the data will be made available for reuse. If any constraints exist, an embargo period will be mentioned in Table 13 to keep the data for only a period of time.
- The data producers will make their data available for third parties within public repositories. The data will be reused for the scientific publication's validation purpose.

It must be also mentioned that common metadata that will be used for SECASSURED project data, e.g. "European Union (EU)", "Horizon Europe" the acronym of the project, publication date, etc. as well as the disclaimer to use in any publication but also public dataset that will be stored in ZENODO and/or GitLab will also be taken in account during the FAIR data management.

4.1.1 Naming conventions for SECASSURED documents and data/document versioning

Within the framework of the SECASSURED quality plan and control, a series of documents/reports and templates will and have been created to ensure a consistent approach for all SECASSURED data and their versions. Details about these reports can be found in SECASSURED D8.1 "Project Handbook and quality plan". For purposes of completeness, we have added below some common material to indicate how the data versioning is aligned with the FAIR approach.

Partners use the Microsoft Teams server of the project for the development of the documents, which enable collaborative writing and track changes functionalities. For any case that versioning management is applied, the guidelines below should be followed:

- The file name should start with "SECASSURED_**"
- The filename should be descriptive of the contents and the author, e.g. "SECASSURED_D14.1_Project handbook and quality plan_SIN_v1.docx"
- When a document is likely to be produced in a similar format by various partners, the partner's short name should be included in the file name.
- When commenting on a document provided by another partner, the filename should be changed to include the initials of the person or short name of the partner making the changes e.g. "SECASSURED_**_SIN_v2_IDK.docx" if changes to the version 2 have been made by IDEKO.
- When suggesting changes to a document, the use of the track changes feature in Word is recommended to assist the document author/owner.
- Only the originating author or owner of a document should increment the version number, i.e. when the author has received and implemented all changes to the second version of the document, it becomes "SECASSURED_**_IDK_v3.docx".

4.2 Contribution to the open research data

Open Access (see Figure 4) refers to providing online access to scientific information that is freely available to end users and can be reused in multiple ways. In the context of research and innovation, "scientific information" includes peer-reviewed research articles published in scholarly journals, as well as research data (including data underlying publications, curated datasets, and raw data).

Figure 4 – Open Access in H2020 projects

To maximize access to and reuse of research data generated by SECASSURED, while balancing openness with the protection of scientific information, commercialization, intellectual property rights (IPR), privacy, and security considerations, the project will adopt the following approach:

In parallel with the publication of scientific articles, SECASSURED will deposit the corresponding underlying research data needed to validate the results presented in these publications. The publication of data will be voluntary, fully aligned with SECASSURED’s intellectual property and patenting activities. It is recognized that some data cannot be made openly accessible, and the principle of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” will be applied.

Where appropriate, SECASSURED aims to contribute datasets to the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP). Candidate datasets for sharing will be carefully reviewed to ensure that:

- They do not contain confidential, commercially sensitive, or personal information (in accordance with GDPR).
- Permission from relevant stakeholders or data owners has been obtained.
- Sharing the data does not compromise exploitation opportunities or IP protection.

A public repository will be created in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/secassured>) and GitLab to deposit Open Data following the FAIR principles, ensuring that data are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. The next version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) will provide detailed information on which datasets will be open, how they will be exploited or made available for verification and reuse, and how they will be curated and preserved.

Datasets will be reviewed by the respective Data Owners and must be approved before being considered for open access. Data Owners, together with the relevant technical consortium partners, will agree on the licensing (e.g., Creative Commons or public domain). Once approved in principle, the dataset will be made available to the SECASSURED user community and uploaded to relevant open-access repositories. For data subject to embargo due to IP protection or exploitation concerns, a release timeline will be established.

Approval for making data openly available must be communicated to the Project Coordinator via email by the Data Owners. This approval must explicitly include consent for distribution outside the consortium and should contain the following information:

Table 21 - Open Data Ownerships

Data Owner	Description of data	Data filenames and version	Consent to publish data outside the SECASSURED consortium
<i>Who is the data owner</i>	<i>What the data include</i>	<i>Filenames and depository position</i>	<i>[YES/NO]</i>

4.2.1 Structure for open research data compilation

Once data sets have been published publicly, this section shows the structure that SECASSURED project will follow to present all data made available through the ZENODO and GitLab platform for Open Research Pilot.

- Title: Title of the openly publicised document
- Overview: Short summary of the publicised document.
- Authors Name of authors and Company
- Publication date: Date of publication
- Digital Object Identifier: Digital Object Identifier of the publication
- Files

Name	Size
Name of files shared by ZENODO	Size (in MB or KB)

- License (For Files):
- References: Reference to the publication (i.e: DOI, etc.)

5 Ethics considerations

It is assumed that all data to be collected from stakeholders in the project will be done in accordance with applicable ethical standards and requirements in the respective countries of the data collection, as well will be processed and handled in a secure way and in line with applicable rules and regulations on privacy and data protection.

Specific articles of the Grant Agreement (GA) mandate that all ethical principles comply to the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, avoiding fabrication, falsification, plagiarism or other research misconduct. In chapter 4, section 4 of the GA, Article 34 ETHICS AND RESEARCH INTEGRITY and Article 39 PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA, dictate the roles and responsibilities of each consortium partner, since they are beneficiaries of the SECASSURED. Towards SECASSURED's objectives, the beneficiaries have full responsibility for implementing the action and complying with the provisions of the GA. Regarding compliance with Ethics principles, each beneficiary must submit to the coordinator in good time notifications for activities raising ethical issues. Additionally, obligations of all partners related to Data management are described in the other sections of this deliverable.

6 General data protection policy (GDPR)

As of May 2018, the GDPR has been applicable in all Member States in the European Union, as well as in the countries in the European Economic Area (EEA).

Data confidentiality is an overriding concern throughout the SECASSURED project and beyond, as the SECASSURED framework will continue to be used afterwards, thus SECASSURED aims at being fully GDPR compliant. All data to be collected from stakeholders in the project will be done in accordance with applicable ethical standards and requirements in the respective countries of the data collection, as well will be processed and handled in a secure way and in line with applicable rules and regulations on privacy and data protection.

Table 14 below presents the data and personal information that is planned to be collected and stored throughout the project duration and beyond as well as their access, storage, purpose and retention details.

Table 22 - Data and Personal Information from day-to-day activities

Personal Data Description ²	Access ³	Storage ⁴	Purpose ⁵	Duration ⁶
Official Contact List of SECASSURED contacts	Internal to SECASSURED (project partners only)	SECASSURED's Microsoft Teams Server (team: SECASSURED - Consortium, <i>folder: SECASSURED Contacts</i>)	Management, organizations contact points	30/11/2026
Meetings' related material (agendas, presentations, signature lists, minutes)	Internal to SECASSURED (project partners only)	SECASSURED's Microsoft Teams Server (team: SECASSURED - Consortium, <i>folder: Meetings</i>)	Knowledge sharing, dissemination and management reasons	30/11/2026
Workshops/Conferences and Training sessions	Internal and external to SECASSURED	SECASSURED's Microsoft Teams Server	Large event dissemination	30/11/2026

² Overall data description.

³ Determines who has access to the particular data (internal, external to consortium).

⁴ Storage places of actual data.

⁵ Intended purpose of data and reasons for keeping.

⁶ Duration of stored data (until when they will be kept).

		(team: SECASSURED - Consortium, <i>folder: Meetings, SECASSURED Website</i>)		
Reporting (C forms)	Internal to SECASSURED (project partners only)	SECASSURED's Microsoft Teams Server (team: SECASSURED - Consortium, <i>folder: Project's Official Documents</i>)	SECASSURED reporting and consolidation of financial reports	5 years after the project's end

Deliverables, official documents and other SECASSURED reports	Depending on deliverable type could be public or consortium restricted	SECASSURED's Microsoft Teams Server (team: SECASSURED - Consortium, <i>folder: Project's Official Documents</i>)	SECASSURED documents and deliverables	30/11/2026
Publications	Internal and external to SECASSURED	SECASSURED's Microsoft Teams Server (team: SECASSURED - Consortium, <i>folder: Project's Official Documents</i>)	Dissemination and publication of research results	Internal: 30/11/2026 External: Depending on publisher

6.1 Security of Data

As a security engineering project, SECASSURED applies a security-by-design and security-by-default approach to all data throughout its lifecycle. This applies to internally generated data, third-party

datasets, software artefacts, and metadata. The objective is to ensure confidentiality, integrity, availability, authenticity, and traceability, while complying with GDPR, IPR, and contractual obligations.

Each dataset is assigned a responsible Work Package (WP) and data owner, who ensures that appropriate security controls are implemented. For third-party data, all processing and sharing activities strictly follow the conditions defined in data sharing agreements and licenses. Access to data repositories and platforms is granted based on the principle of least privilege and role-based access control.

Data are classified according to confidentiality levels (e.g., Public, Project Consortium, Restricted, Confidential), and protection measures are applied proportionally. Sensitive or restricted data are stored in controlled environments, with secure transmission protocols (e.g., encrypted communication) used for data exchange between partners and with third parties. Backups and integrity checks are performed to prevent data loss and detect corruption or unauthorized modification.

Metadata supports not only FAIR compliance but also security by documenting provenance, ownership, versioning, and usage restrictions. Version control systems and logging mechanisms enhance traceability and accountability, particularly for software and data processing workflows developed under DevOps, SecDevOps, and MLOps practices.

In the event of a security incident or identified data integrity issue, the responsible partner must inform the WP lead. Corrective actions may include restricting access, updating or withdrawing affected datasets, revising metadata, and notifying relevant stakeholders in line with legal and contractual requirements.

At the end of the project, data are securely archived or deleted according to retention policies and third-party agreements. Secure disposal methods are applied where required to prevent unauthorized recovery.

Through these measures, SECASSURED ensures that data security is embedded across the full lifecycle and supply chain, safeguarding both internal and externally sourced data while enabling trustworthy and compliant research outcomes.

7 Conclusions

This SECASSURED Data Management Plan (DMP) provides a comprehensive overview of the data generated, processed, and used within the scope of the project, as well as the mechanisms put in place to manage them. It includes a detailed description of the type and nature of data associated with each SECASSURED work package, highlighting their relevance to the project's objectives. A structured approach has been developed to ensure that SECASSURED's data management practices align with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), as recommended by the European Commission.

A dedicated section of this report addresses the management of personal data in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). This regulation harmonizes data privacy legislation across Europe, protecting the rights of EU citizens while guiding organizations on proper data handling practices. The section outlines the procedures and practices SECASSURED will follow to comply with GDPR, including the use of consent forms and internal processes designed to safeguard personal data throughout the project.

Appendix

8 ANNEX I: Data management report

Indicator	Means of verification	Target Values	Compliance
			WPx
Data Creation			
Format	Compliance with existing standards of data exchange	XLS, XML etc.	√ or ×
Availability and Readability	Whole package of data available, non-corruption, whole percentage collected	100% received 100% accessible	√ or ×
Fit for Use	Data follow data compliancy for proper processing and review	100% usable by intended beneficiary/ies	√ or ×
Consistency and Completeness	Data are consistent and complete for the intended purpose	Including 100% of information for the intended purpose	√ or ×
Relation	Data follow a precise relation to their purpose	100% purpose precision	√ or ×
Data Processing and Analysis			
Data logic	Data can be and are processed following a concise logic and approach	New and processed data follow precise data logic	√ or ×
Organization and Utility	Suitable content organization of data under processing	100% organized data	√ or ×
Validation	Ensuring that the data under processing are correct and relevant	100% validated and relevant data	√ or ×
Aggregation	Whenever multiple data need to be aggregated ensure that this is done in a concise approach	100% aggregate-able data	√ or ×
Transformation	Transformation of data to the proper format(s) for processing	Capability of data for transformation (if needed)	√ or ×
Calibration	Calibration of data for their intended purpose	Data properly calibrated	√ or ×
Data Publication and Utilization			
Means-independent	Transferring of the data in a means-independent approach	100% means independent transferability	√ or ×
Security (a)	Data stored in a secure enough server	At least access control provided over a TLS protocol	√ or ×
Data Storage, Archiving and Re-Use			

Up to date	Ensuring that the stored data are up to date for the specific purpose and no later version exists	100% updated	√ or ×
Meta Data	Existence of meta data in stored files	Relevant metadata have been included into the archive per data set	√ or ×
Security (b)	Access control provided	Access control setup	√ or ×
Security (c)	Server is considered as safe enough (TLS connection protocol)	At least TLS connection configuration	√ or ×
Bandwidth	Control of server bandwidth	Effective storage server bandwidth > 2 MBPS	√ or ×
Expiration	Properly setting expiration dates for all data after which the data will be deleted	Expiration date noted	√ or ×